

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

A REVIEW ON FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ATENOLOL FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Zaki Iqbal Ansari*, Dr. Avish D Maru, Mr. Yashpal More

Department of Pharmaceutics, Loknete Dr J D Pawar College of Pharmacy Manur (Kalwan), Maharashtra.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 18/09/2021

Available online
31/10/2021

Keywords

Atenolol;
Gastro Retentive Floating
Drug Delivery Systems;
Hydrodynamically Balanced
Systems;
Hydroxypropyl Methyl
Cellulose.

ABSTRACT

Gastro retentive floating drug delivery systems (GFDDS) of Atenolol, an antihypertensive drug, with an oral bioavailability of only 50% (because of its poor absorption from lower gastrointestinal tract) have been designed. Methocel, polysaccharides (e.g., chitosan), was used as the polymer and sodium bicarbonate as gas generating agent to reduce floating lag time. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method. The optimized formulation containing Atenolol 100 mg, Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose 35 mg and Sodium bicarbonate 35 mg has displayed almost first order release kinetics with a floating lag time of only 101 second. This formulation released more than 96% drug in 6 hours. This study proves that GFDDS of Atenolol can be designed using, Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose as polymer, which provides nearly first order release kinetics and thus possible enhancement of oral bioavailability of the drug.

Corresponding author

Zaki Iqbal Ansari

Department of Pharmaceutics,
Loknete Dr J D Pawar College of Pharmacy,
Manur (Kalwan), Maharashtra.

Please cite this article in press as **Zaki Iqbal Ansari et al.** A Review on Formulation and Evaluation of Atenolol Floating Drug Delivery System. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2021;11(10).

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INTRODUCTION

Oral route is the preferred route of administration of drugs because of low cost of therapy ease of administration and more of patient compliance. But the poor bioavailability of orally administered drugs is still a challenging one, though extensive advancements in drug discovery process are made. The floating drugs delivery system of drug is predominant method for sustained release of various drugs. Oral sustain drug delivery system is complicated by limited gastric residence time (GRTs) Rapid GI transit can prevent complete drug release in the absorption zone and reduce the efficiency of the administration dose. Since the majority of drugs are absorbed in stomach or upper part of small intestine. To overcome these limitations, several controlled oral drug delivery systems with prolonged gastric residence time have been reported recently such as floating drug delivery system in order to increase the gastric residence time and better sustained effect. Drug absorption from gastrointestinal tract is complex procedure and is subjected to many variables. It has been reported that the extent of GIT drug absorption is related to contact time with the small intestinal mucosa. Gastro retentive system can remain in the gastric region for several hours and therefore significantly prolong the gastric residence time of drugs. {1}

Floating drug delivery system or hydrodynamically balanced system (HBS) is a formulation of drug in gel forming hydrocolloid meant to remain buoyant on stomach contents. This not only prolongs GI residence time but also does so in an area of the GIT that would maximize drug reaching its absorption site. By selection of polymer with proper molecular weight and swelling properties controlled and sustained drug release can be achieved. {1}

Mucoadhesive and bio adhesive system:

Bio adhesive drug delivery system are used to localize a delivery device within the lumen to enhance the drug absorption in a site-specific manner. This approach involves the use of bio adhesive polymers which adhere to the most promising excipients that have been used commonly in this system include polycarboxylic, Carbopol, lectins, chitosan and glidant etc. {1}

Classification of Floating drug delivery system based on buoyancy.

A. Single unit:

Single unit dosage forms are easiest to develop but suffers from the risk of losing their effects too early due to their all or none they may cause high variability in bioavailability and local irritation due to large amount of drug delivered at a particular site of the gastro intestinal tract.

a.Non effervescent system

One or more gel forming highly swellable cellulosic hydrocolloids (e.g., Hydroxyl ethyl cellulose, hydroxyl propyl cellulose hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) and sodium carboxy methyl cellulose, polysaccharides or matrix forming polymers are incorporated in high level (25-70% W/W) to tablets or capsules. For the preparation of these types of systems the drugs and gel forming hydrocolloid are mixed thoroughly. After oral administration this dosage form swells in contact with gastric fluids and attains a bulk density of <1.

The air entrapped within the swollen matrix in parts buoyancy to the dosage form. The formed swollen gel like structure acts as a reservoir and allows sustained release of drug through the gelatinous mass.

b. Effervescent system or gas generating system.

These are matrix types of systems prepared with the help of swellable polymers such as methylcellulose and chitosan and various effervescent compounds.

e.g., sodium bicarbonate, tartaric acid, and citric acid. They are formulated in such a way that when in contact with the acidic gastric contents, CO₂ is liberated and gets entrapped in swollen hydrocolloids, which provides buoyancy to the dosage forms. The optimal stoichiometric ratio of citric acid and sodium bicarbonate for gas generation is reported to be 0.76:1

B: Multiple Unit System:

Single unit formulations are associated with problems such as sticking together or being obstructed in gastrointestinal tract, which may have a potential danger of producing irritation. Multiple unit systems avoid the „all-or-none“ gastric emptying nature of single unit systems. It reduces the inter subject variability in absorption and the probability for dose dumping is lower

a.Non effervescent systems:

A little or no much report was found in the literature on non-effervescent multiple unit systems, as compared to the effervescent systems. However, few workers have reported the possibility of developing such system containing indomethacin, using chitosan as the polymeric excipient^{12,13}. A multiple unit HBS containing indomethacin as a model drug prepared by extrusion process is reported. A mixture of drug, chitosan and acetic acid is extruded through a needle, and the extrudate is cut and dried. Chitosan hydrates float in the acidic media, and the required drug release could be obtained by modifying the drug polymer ratio.

b. Effervescent systems:

A multiple unit system comprises of calcium alginate core and calcium alginate/PVA membrane, both separated by an air compartment was prepared. In presence of water, the PVA leaches out and increases the membrane permeability, maintaining the integrity of the air compartment. Increase in molecular weight and concentration of PVA, resulted in enhancement of the floating properties of the system. Freeze-drying technique is also reported for the preparation of floating calcium alginate beads. Sodium alginate solution is added drop wise in to the aqueous solution of calcium chloride, causing the instant gelation of the droplet surface, due to the formation of calcium alginate. The obtained beads are freeze dried resulting in a porous structure which aid in floating. The authors studied the behavior of radio labelled floating beads and compared with non-floating beads in human volunteers using gamma scintigraphy. Prolonged gastric residence time of more than 5.5 hr was observed for floating beads. The non-floating beads had a shorter residence time with a mean onset emptying time of 1 hr.

c. Floating microspheres:

A controlled release system designed to increase its residence time in the stomach without contact with the mucosa was achieved through the preparation of floating microspheres. Techniques involved in their preparation include simple solvent evaporation, and solvent diffusion and evaporation. The drug release and better floating properties mainly depend on the type of polymer, plasticizer and the solvents employed for the preparation. Polymers, such as polycarbonate, Eudragit RS¹⁶ and cellulose acetate, are used in the preparation of hollow microspheres, and the drug release can be modified by optimizing the amount of polymer and the polymer-plasticizer ratio.

C. Raft forming systems:

The basic mechanism involved in the raft formation includes the formation of viscous cohesive gel in contact with gastric fluids, wherein each portion of the liquid swells forming a continuous layer called a raft. The raft floats because of the buoyancy created by the formation of CO₂ and act as a barrier to prevent the reflux of gastric contents like HCl and enzymes into the esophagus. Usually, the system contains a gel forming agent and alkaline bicarbonates or carbonates responsible for the formation of to make the system less dense and float on the gastric fluids. Reckitt and Colman Products Ltd. have come out with such formulation in the treatment of H. pylori infections of GIT.

Atenolol is a beta-adrenoreceptor antagonist or more commonly known as a beta-blocker used in the treatment of hypertension and angina pectoris. It is incompletely absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract and has an oral bioavailability of only 50%, while the remaining is excreted unchanged in feces. This is because of its poor absorption in lower gastrointestinal tract. It undergoes little or no hepatic first pass metabolism and its elimination half-life is 6 to 7 hours. Therefore, it is selected as a suitable drug for the design of a gastro-retentive floating drug delivery system (GFDDS) with a view to improve its oral bioavailability. {3}

Table No:01. List of Drugs which are marketed as FDDS:

Brand name	Drug	Clinical Importance	Dosage form
Madopar [®]	Levodopa	Parkinsonism	Capsule
	Benserazide		
Cytotec [®]	Misoprostal	Gastric ulcer	Capsule
Valrelease [®]	Diazepam	Sedative –hypnotic	Capsule
Conviron	Ferrous sulphate	Pernicious anemia	Capsule
Liquid Gavison [®]	Al. hydroxide, Mg. carbonate	Heart burn	Liquid alginate preparation Liquid alginate preparation
Topalkan [®]	Al-Mg antacid	Antacid	Tablet
Cifran OD [®]	Ciprofloxacin	Urinary tract infection Genital Urinary, respiratory, Gastro- intestinal infection	Tablet
Oflin OD [®]	Ofloxacin		Tablet
Prolopa [®]	Propranolol	Hypertension	Tablet
Amalgate	Amalgate	Antacid	Tablet
Flotacoat [®]			
Halo [™]	Propranolol	Hypertension	Tablet

Table No.02.List of drugs prepared as FDDS:

S.No.	DOSAGE FORM	DRUGS
1.	Microspheres	Metformin hydrochloride, ketoprofen, Aspirin, Verapamil, Griseofulvin, <i>P</i> -nitroaniline, Ibuprofen,
2.	Granules	Diclofenac sodium, Indomethacin, Prednisolone
3.	Capsules	Chlordiazepoxide HCl, Diazepam, Frusemide, L-Dopa and Benderizine, Misoprostol, Propranolol
4.	Tablets/Pills	Phenytoin hydrochloride, 5 fluoro uracil, Furosemide,

Advantages Of Floating DosageForm:

1. These systems are particularly advantageous for drugs that are specifically absorbed from stomach or the proximal part of the small intestine, e.g., riboflavin and furosemide.
2. The fluctuations in plasma drug concentration are minimized, and concentration-dependent adverse effects that are associated with peak concentrations can be prevented. This feature is of special importance for drugs with a narrow therapeutic index.
3. The efficacy of the medicaments administered utilizing the sustained release principle of floating formulation has been found to be independent of the site of particular medicaments.
4. Complete absorption of the drug from the floating dosage form is expected even at the alkaline pH of the intestine. The dissolution of the drug in gastric fluid occurs and then the dissolved drug is available for absorption in the small intestine after emptying of the stomach contents.^{11,19}
5. Poor absorption is expected when there is vigorous intestinal movement and a shorted transit time as might occur in certain type of diarrhea. Under such circumstances it may be advantageous to keep the drug in floating condition in stomach to get a relatively better response.
6. Drugs that have poor bioavailability because of site-specific absorption from the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract are potential candidates to be formulated as floating drug delivery systems, thereby maximizing their absorption. A significant increase in the bioavailability of floating dosage forms (42.9%) could be achieved as compared with commercially available LASIX tablets (33.4%) and enteric-coated LASIX-long product (29.5%) {4}

Limitations Of Floating Drug Delivery Systems:

1. A high level of fluid in the stomach is required for drug delivery to float and work efficiently.
2. Drugs which have stability and solubility problems in GIT are not suitable candidates for these types of systems.
3. Drugs such as nifedipine, which undergo first pass metabolism may not be desirable for the preparation of these types of systems.
4. Drugs which are irritant to Gastric mucosa are also not desirable.
5. The drug substances that are unstable in the acidic environment of the stomach are not suitable candidates to be incorporated in the systems. {5}

Application of FDDS:

Floating drug delivery offers several applications for drugs having poor bioavailability because of the narrow absorption window in the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract. It retains the dosage form at the site of absorption and thus enhances the bioavailability. These are summarized as follows.

Sustained Drug Delivery:

HBS systems can remain in the stomach for long periods and hence can release the drug over a prolonged period of time. The problem of short gastric residence time encountered with an oral CR formulation hence can be overcome with these systems. These systems have a bulk density of Eg. Sustained release floating capsules of nifedipine hydrochloride were developed and were evaluated in vivo. The formulation compared with commercially available MICARD capsules using rabbits. Plasma concentration time curves showed a longer duration for administration (16 hours) in the sustained release floating capsules as compared with conventional MICARD capsules (8 hours).

Site-Specific Drug Delivery:

These systems are particularly advantageous for drugs that are specifically absorbed from stomach or the proximal part of the small intestine, e.g., riboflavin and furosemide. Eg. Furosemide is primarily absorbed from the stomach followed by the duodenum. It has been reported that a monolithic floating dosage form with prolonged gastric residence time was developed and the bioavailability was increased. AUC obtained with the floating tablets was approximately 1.8 times those of conventional furosemide tablets.

Absorption Enhancement:

Drugs that have poor bioavailability because of site-specific absorption from the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract are potential candidates to be formulated as floating drug delivery systems, thereby maximizing their absorption. e.g. A significant increase in the bioavailability of floating dosage forms (42.9%) could be achieved as compared with commercially available LASIX tablets (33.4%) and enteric-coated LASIX-long product (29.5%). {6}

CONCLUSION

Floating drug delivery system have come forward as an efficient means of enhancing the bioavailability and controlled delivery of drugs. The advancement in delivery technology will lead to the development of large number of floating delivery system to optimize the delivery of molecules that exhibit absorption window, low bioavailability and extensive first pass metabolism. {7}

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